

PHASE CHANGE CHARACTERISTICS OF PCM FOR COOL THERMAL ENERGY STORAGE APPLICATION

A PROJECT REPORT

submitted by

RAKESH. R (119009146)

towards partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of the degree

of

Bachelor of Technology in Mechanical Engineering

School of Mechanical Engineering

SASTRA (Deemed to be University)

Tirumalaisamudram, Thanjavur - 613401

Tamilnadu, INDIA

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BONAFIDE CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the project work entitled "**PHASE CHANGE CHARACTERISTICS OF PCM FOR COOL THERMAL ENERGY STORAGE APPLICATION**" is a bonafide record of the work carried out by

RAKESH. R (119009146)

student of final year B.Tech., Mechanical Engineering, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the award of the degree of B.Tech in Mechanical Engineering of the

SASTRA DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY, Tirumalaisamudram, Thanjavur - 613401, during the year 2018-2019.

NAME OF THE INTERNAL GUIDE : Mr. Paul Joshua S

SIGNATURE

Project Viva-voce held on _____

Examiner - I

Examiner - II

SASTRA Deemed University
Thanjavur – 613 401
Tamilnadu, India

FEEDBACK FROM ON-SITE INTERNSHIP MENTOR / GUIDE

1. Name of Student: Rakesh. R
2. Registration Number: 119009146
3. Program & Branch of Study: B.Tech – Mechanical Engineering
4. Duration of Internship: 02.01.2019 to 11.04.2019 (4 months)
5. Name of Organisation where internship was completed with complete address:
College of Engineering, Guindy Campus,
Anna University,
Chennai - 600025
6. Internship topic: Phase change characteristics of PCM for cool thermal energy storage application
7. Name & designation of on-site mentor / guide: Dr. V. Kumaresan,
Associate Professor, Head in-charge,
Refrigeration and Air-conditioning division,
Department of Mechanical Engineering,
College of Engineering, Guindy Campus,
Anna University,
Chennai - 600025
8. Contact Details: Phone: 044-22357590
e-Mail: kumaresanv@annauniv.edu
: kumaresanvm1973@gmail.com

TO BE FILLED BY THE ON-SITE MENTOR / GUIDE

Kindly provide your candidate feedback on the student's performance during the internship period. You may kindly rank the students on a scale of 1 to 5, with 5 being Most Satisfied and 1 being Least Satisfied.

1. Fundamental knowledge of the student	1	2	3	4	5
2. Independent contribution by the student	1	2	3	4	5
3. Willingness to learn new concepts	1	2	3	4	5
4. Job knowledge & application Skills	1	2	3	4	5
5. Personal skills	1	2	3	4	5
6. Adherence to organisational rules	1	2	3	4	5

Any other comments and suggestions:

Signature of on-site mentor / guide

Name **Dr. V. KUMARESAN, M.E., Ph.D.**
Associate Professor
Department of Mechanical Engineering
College of Engineering Guindy Campus
Anna University, Chennai-600 025.

Date: 11/4/19.

Official Seal

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Rakesh. R

Chennai, 2019

ABSTRACT

KEY WORDS: thermal energy storage; cooling; PCM; bath temperature; capsule size

The key concern in today's world is reducing the disparity of energy supply and demand by storing it. To reduce the greenhouse emissions, there has been a paradigm shift to utilize renewable sources of energy. To alleviate these concerns, the need to operate buildings more efficiently becomes an urgent objective.

The sun's rays are one of the potential sources of renewable energy. Thermal Energy Storage (TES) is a technique used for storing and releasing of renewable energy in the form of sensible heat, latent heat and chemical heat. It uses standard cooling equipment, plus an energy storage tank to shift all or a portion of a building's cooling needs to off-peak hours, during which the demand is low. Latent heat can be stored without a significant change of the temperature of the material, an almost isothermal process; that is why PCMs can be used for temperature control of TES applications. Considering the pressing need to reduce or eliminate the major problem of subcooling in water, at a minimum cost, the main objective of the present work is to investigate the solidification characteristics of water dispersed with the natural graphite flake additives at various concentrations in a spherical encapsulation for various parameters such **water bath temperature** and the **size of the capsule**.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

	Page
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	(i)
ABSTRACT.....	(ii)
LIST OF FIGURES.....	(iv)
ABBREVIATIONS.....	(v)
NOTATIONS.....	(vi)
CHAPTER 1	
BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION.....	(1)
CHAPTER 2	
ENERGY STORAGE.....	(3)
CHAPTER 3	
THERMAL COMFORT.....	(8)
CHAPTER 4	
PHASE CHANGE MATERIALS.....	(11)
CHAPTER 5	
ELIMINATION OF SUBCOOLING.....	(15)
CHAPTER 6	
MATERIALS AND METHODS.....	(17)
CHAPTER 7	
EXPERIMENTAL SETUP.....	(19)
CHAPTER 8	
RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS.....	(22)
CHAPTER 9	
CONCLUSION.....	(29)
CHAPTER 10	
REFERENCES.....	(30)

List of figures

Figure No.	Figure name	Page No.
4.1	Classifications of PCMs	13
6.1	Probe sonication with a frequency of 15kHz	18
6.2	Preparation of water based PCM	18
7.1	Experimental Setup	20
7.2	Position of RTDs inside the encapsulated sphere	21
7.3	Schematic diagram of the experimental setup	21
8.1	T-t history of (a) 50mL (b) 100mL of DI water during solidification	22
8.2	T-t history of (a) 1 wt.% (b) 2 wt.% (c) 3 wt.% of NGF added to 50mL of PCM with external bath temperature -7°C	24
8.3	T-t history of (a) 1 wt.% (b) 2 wt.% (c) 3 wt.% of NGF added to 50mL of PCM with external bath temperature -9°C	25
8.4	T-t history of (a) 1 wt.% (b) 2 wt.% (c) 3 wt.% of NGF added to 100mL of PCM with external bath temperature -7°C	26
8.5	T-t history of (a) 1 wt.% (b) 2 wt.% (c) 3 wt.% of NGF added to 100mL of PCM with external bath temperature -9°C	28

ABBREVIATIONS

DHW	Domestic Hot Water
DI	De-ionized
GNP	Graphene nanoplatelets
HTF	Heat Transfer Fluid
LHTES	Latent Heat Thermal Energy Storage
MWCNT	Multiwalled Carbon nanotubes
NGF	Natural Graphite Flake
PCM	Phase Change Material
PTDC	Proportionate Temperature Differential Controller
PUF	Polyurethane foam
RTD	Resistance Temperature Detector
SHTES	Sensible Heat Thermal Energy Storage
TCES	Thermochemical Energy Storage
TES	Thermal Energy Storage

NOTATIONS

English Symbols

C_p	Specific heat of the material used to store thermal energy
m	Mass of material used to store thermal energy
Q	Amount of thermal energy stored or released
T_1	Initial Temperature
T_2	Final Temperature
T_{mp}	Ideal melting-peak temperature of the phase-change process of pure PCM
ΔT_m	Phase change melting temperature range
T_{sp}	Solidifying temperature of PCM

Greek Symbols

λ	Latent heat of fusion
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CHAPTER 1

BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

The key concern in today's world is reducing the disparity of supply and energy demand by storing it. To reduce the greenhouse emissions, there was a paradigm shift to utilize renewable sources of energy. Of late, energy demand has increased exponentially owing to the high energy utilization in various fields. The powers driving energy demand, led by solid financial development, outpaced advance on energy efficiency. Fossil fuels have been satisfying every single human energy need for long time, but these non-renewable energy sources have caused a great deal of harm to the environment, that it has increased the rate of worldwide temperature alteration. The long-term warming trend has continued in 2018, with the average global temperature set to be the fourth highest on record. The 20 warmest years on record have been in the past 22 years, with the top four in the past four years, according to the World Meteorological Organization [1]

The costs of these non-renewable energy sources have exponentially increased in the past few years and it is expected to keep increasing in the upcoming years, since there is a surge in the energy demand while petroleum products are diminishing. As a result, there is a need for humans to look at alternative sources of energy and avoid petroleum derivatives. It is noticeable that an expansion propensity in energy demand has taken place because of the impacts of environmental change. In view of the above circumstances, the integration of renewable energy sources is the ideal way to diminish the use of exhaustible sources of energy and counterbalance the expansion in cooling load.

In energy efficiency, there is a rising concern is to address energy security and supportability concerns. All the development comes from developing economies, pioneered by countries such as India. Studies say that over 60% or more of many countries' total energy consumption can be from renewable sources by 2050. For instance, India and the United States could see shares increase to 66% or more. [2]

In India, primary energy demand increased to 4.1%, well above the five-year average annual rate of 3.2% since 2012 but lower than the ten-year average rate of 4.7% since 2007[3]. By 2050, all countries can substantially increase the proportion of renewable energy in their total energy use. India is advancing towards its target to achieve 175GW of renewable power capacity by 2022 In 2015, 36% of India's energy use were accounted by renewable sources. [4]

The need for energy is likely to grow even more in the 21st century with the improvements in living standards across the planet; moreover, the economic development of pan-Asian nation, like China and India, has emphasized the problem of energy demand. It becomes necessary to deploy heating, ventilating and air conditioning systems in order to provide a comfortable environment for occupants. The energy consumed in buildings accounts for around 30%-40% of the world's energy consumption, making buildings the largest energy consumer [5]. The energy consumption for residential and commercial buildings in India is expected to increase by an average of 2.7% per year between 2015 and 2040, more than twice the global average increase [6]. Commercial buildings are the third largest consumers of energy in India after industry and agriculture. To accommodate these new resources, the need to operate buildings more efficiently becomes an urgent objective.

CHAPTER 2

ENERGY STORAGE

Energy storage not only reduces the mismatch between supply and demand but also improves the performance and reliability of energy systems and plays an important role in conserving energy. Storage of energy would improve the performance of a power generation plant by load leveling and a higher efficiency would lead to energy conservation and lesser generation cost.

Thermal energy storage (TES) is a technology that stocks thermal energy by heating or cooling a storage medium so that the stored energy can be used at a later time for heating and cooling applications and power generation. TES systems are used particularly in buildings and industrial processes. In these applications, approximately half of the energy consumed is in the form of thermal energy, the demand for which may vary during any given day and from one day to next.

They can also reduce peak demand, energy consumption, CO₂ emissions and costs, while increasing overall efficiency of energy systems. Furthermore, the conversion and storage of variable renewable energy in the form of thermal energy can also help increase the share of renewables in the energy mix.

There are three kinds of TES systems, namely:

1. sensible heat storage that is based on storing thermal energy by heating or cooling a liquid or solid storage medium (e.g. water, sand, molten salts, rocks), with water being the cheapest option;

2. latent heat storage using phase change materials or PCMs (e.g. from a solid state into a liquid state)
3. thermo-chemical energy storage (TCES) using chemical reactions to store and release thermal energy.

Sensible Heat Thermal Energy Storage (SHTES) system

The SHTES system stores energy by raising the material's temperature, without the material undergoing any phase change. The amount of energy stored depends on the mass of the storage material, the specific heat capacity, and the temperature change. The amount of thermal energy stored in the form of sensible heat can be calculated by:

$$Q = \int_{T_1}^{T_2} mC_p dT \quad (2.1)$$
$$= mC_p(T_2 - T_1)$$

where Q is the amount of thermal energy stored or released in the form of sensible heat (kJ), T₁ is the initial temperature (K), T₂ is the final temperature (K), m is the mass of material used to store thermal energy (kg), C_p is the specific heat of the material used to store thermal energy (kJ kg⁻¹ K⁻¹)

The most popular technology in this category is the use of hot-water tanks, being is a cost-effective option used as a buffer for domestic hot water (DHW) storage. Materials can be selected upon their thermal properties and the required operational temperature and storage capacity. The examples of sensible heat storage materials used today are liquids such as oil, molten salt, and water, e.g. in solar power plants (Gil et al., 2010) and in chilled water storage

(Rosiek & Garrido, 2012). The Solid TES materials, such as rock and concrete are used for underground storage (Al-Dabbas & Al-Rousan, 2013) and in building a structure (Ståhl, 2009) [7,8,9,10]. Vapors and gases are however less utilized due to their lower volumetric density in comparison to liquids and solids. The inherent disadvantages associated with sensible heat storage are the low storage density per degree temperature change and the large temperature range for storing the energy.

Thermo-Chemical Energy Storage system

Thermo-Chemical Energy Storage (TCES) is based on storing/ releasing a large amount of thermal energy using chemical reactions and/or reversible physical sorption processes (Zalba et al., 2003) [11]. The basic principle of TCES is that a chemical compound is broken by the addition of heat and the divided components are stored separately until there is a demand. During periods of high demand, the components are reunited into a chemical compound and heat is released. The released heat from the reaction constitutes the storage capacity. This makes TCES particularly suitable for large-scale electricity generating. Thermo-chemical reactions can be used to accumulate and discharge cold and heat on demand but also to regulate humidity in a variety of applications using different chemical reactants. TCES materials have among the highest energy density of all storage media, and hence this technology is what the future beckons. However, storage technologies based on TCES are mostly under development and demonstration and further improvements are necessary to make this technology commercially available.

Latent Heat Thermal Energy Storage System

Latent heat is stored through a change of material phase between solid, liquid or gas. “Latent heat storage” refers to thermal energy stored isothermally, which is the situation during an ideal phase change process. Excess energy available can be used in the peak time if stored properly. The most commonly used PCMs undergo a solid-liquid phase change, for they present large heat storage density and small volume change between the two phases. Nevertheless, the latent heat of vaporization (liquid-vapor) is not utilized in LHTES applications, as it is accompanied by a large change in volume. The amount of thermal energy stored in the form of latent heat in a material is calculated by

$$Q = m\lambda \quad (2.2)$$

where Q is the amount of thermal energy stored or released in form of latent heat (kJ), m is the mass of the material used to store thermal energy (kg), λ is the latent heat of fusion in (kJ kg^{-1}). The conception of LHTES improves two drawbacks of SHTES. One is related to the discharge temperature, which is constant for the first and changes for the latter, and the other is related to the specific energy, which can be from five to fourteen times higher in the first compared to the latter. The LHTES systems have proved to be a better choice owing to its positives such as high energy density, uniform energy storage/supply, compactness.

Several developers are working on new materials and techniques for all LHTES systems, including their integration into building walls (e.g. by encapsulating phase change materials into plaster or air vents) and transportation of thermal energy from one place to another. These new applications are just now being commercialized, and their cost, performance and reliability need to be verified.

Phase change materials (PCMs) can offer higher storage capacity and storage efficiencies from 75-90%. In most cases, storage is based on a solid/liquid phase change with energy densities on the order of 100 kWh/ m³ (e.g. ice). PCM building products, like sensible thermal mass, should be considered as part of the overall package of temperature control measures in a building. These include insulation, shading, building orientation and ventilation.

CHAPTER 3

THERMAL COMFORT

The demand for thermal comfort in both residential and non-residential buildings is currently mounting. The added energy demand significantly contributes to its depletion with a peak demand in the temperate and tropical climate zone. To shift the peak energy demand, the thermal mass of buildings can be used to store the thermal energy and reduce indoor temperature variations.

The concept of storing heat within the building walls has been around since 1881. The building's mass plays an important duty in determining the temperature. A heavy building is able to smooth out temperature peaks by virtue of its mass. The use of thermal mass in shelter dates back to the dawn of humans, and until recently has been the prevailing strategy for building climate control in hot regions. A thermally massive building would mean a trade-off with the cost or aesthetics that require buildings to be increasingly light in weight. Incorporating phase change materials (PCMs) into buildings can increase the thermal mass of lightweight structures.

However, a move to lightweight construction raises concerns over internal comfort conditions due to lack of thermal storage properties, resulting in rapid swings of internal temperature. Optimized selection of building materials for making the external envelop also plays an important role in achieving thermal comfort in buildings, where thermal comfort is achieved through passive cooling, strategies. Phase Change Materials (PCMs) are proposed as a solution to reduce energy demands from buildings by the addition of PCMs to construction materials

as concrete, gypsum or plasterboard panels. Recent research has looked at the incorporation of organic PCMs into porous building materials, creating functional and effective building elements which can affect significant energy savings.

The characteristics of PCMs make them inherently suitable for use in buildings for energy conservation purposes without the complications brought about by other thermal storage devices requiring separate plant and space. The improved thermal distribution, cost and space-saving implications are some of the advantages of this type of thermal storage. PCMs have high thermal conductivity so that the temperature gradient required for charging the storage material is small. PCMs have high density, so that a smaller container volume holds the material. PCMs have no chemical decomposition, so that the latent heat storage system life is assured. PCMs don't cause corrosiveness to construction material. Within the human comfort temperature range (approximately 20–28°C), latent heat storage materials have been found to be very effective.

Building materials, such as concrete can store about 1 kJ/kg when subjected to a temperature increase of 1°C, whereas a PCM, such as calcium chloride hexahydrate can store/release up to 193 kJ/kg on complete phase transition (Kenneth and Gates, 2000) [12]. This huge increase of thermal storage capacity for PCMs and their almost isothermal discharge could be used to steady ambient temperatures inside buildings.

Incorporating PCM in wallboards would be of great advantage, as there will be a large surface area in contact with the air inside the building. Among numerous causes that have an influence on energy expenditure and performance of buildings with PCM incorporation, the following parameters are identified:

- Local construction systems: envelope and windows.
- Local climate: solar irradiation and ambient outdoor temperature.
- Internal loads: the number of occupants, electrical appliances (lights, TVs, etc.).

PCM materials can contribute to the energy efficiency of buildings by reducing the peaks in the daily temperature cycles. It may be possible that mechanical air conditioning is not needed at all; as a minimum, the energy consumption for air conditioning can be reduced. And this is how it works: as part of normal overnight ventilation, the warm air in the building is replaced by cold night-time air, which also reduces the temperature of the building's solid structures over the course of the night. PCM can increase the heat capacity of the building, meaning that additional 'coldness' can be stored in the building's structures.

CHAPTER 4

PHASE CHANGE MATERIALS

Latent heat can be stored without a significant change of the temperature of the material; that is why PCMs can be used for temperature control of TES applications. Materials that store thermal energy as latent heat during change of phase either by melting or freezing are called phase change materials (PCM). It should be pointed out that the behavior of common PCMs is slightly different from that of ideal PCMs. In common PCMs, the ideal melting-peak temperature of the isothermal phase-change process of pure PCMs, T_{mp} , is replaced by a phase-change melting temperature range, ΔT_m . The storage capacity of an ideal PCM can be characterized via four main parameters, namely the heat capacity of the solid and liquid phases, the latent heat of fusion and the melting-peak temperature.

As remarked by Mehling and Cabeza [13], if the heat released upon solidification is larger than the sensible heat lost due to subcooling, the temperature rises again to the solidifying temperature of the PCM, T_{sp} , which ideally should be equal to T_{mp} . However, if this does not happen, or if the rate of heat lost to the ambient is larger than the rate of heat released during crystallization, the temperature will not rise to the solidifying temperature again, and a real hysteresis will be caused by subcooling. Therefore, subcooling can cause negative effects when performing dynamic experiments, and it can be a serious problem in technical applications of PCMs. Subcooling can depend on the size of the PCM sample and also on the type and shape of the container used in a macro-scale approach.

The following properties should be possessed by the PCMs for the effective charging / retrieval of the energy in the LHTES systems.

4.1. Thermal properties

- Suitable phase-transition temperature.
- High latent heat of transition.
- Good heat transfer characteristics

4.2. Physical properties

- Favorable phase equilibrium.
- High density.
- Small volume change.
- Low vapor pressure.

4.3. Kinetic properties

- No supercooling.
- Sufficient crystallization rate.

4.4. Chemical properties

- Long-term chemical stability.
- Compatibility with materials of construction.

- No toxicity.
- No fire hazards.

4.5. Economics

- Abundant.
- Available.
- Cost effective

The PCMs are broadly classified into three categories (Organic, Inorganic and Eutectic PCMs) based on their composition as illustrated in Figure:

Figure 4.1 Classifications of PCMs

Organic phase change materials have poorer heat transfer properties, such as lower density, and are more expensive than inorganic salts in general. However, organic materials usually do not suffer segregation and subcooling problems during thermal cycling, which can be a severe

problem for some salt hydrates. Organic materials include paraffin waxes, fatty acids, and sugar alcohols [7]. They have been used in many developmental studies recently. Paraffin waxes have been commercially used for active forced hot-air systems [12]. Salt hydrate phase change materials that have been studied include $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 10\text{H}_2\text{O}$, etc. They offer a range of operating temperatures, melting points ranging from 7 to 117 °C [12]. Salt hydrates have high latent heats of fusion; better heat transfer properties compared to organic materials, and are relatively cheap.

Many phase change materials do not solidify right away when the temperature of the materials is at or below the melting temperature. This phenomenon is called subcooling. During subcooling, the phase change materials are in a metastable state, which implies not being in thermodynamic equilibrium.

CHAPTER 5

ELIMINATION OF SUBCOOLING

Water has been investigated as the potential PCM in the CTES applications due to its high latent heat, abundant availability and ease of handling. However, the existence of subcooling in water delays the onset of solidification and demands the lower evaporator operational temperature in the chiller unit that results with increase in specific energy consumption of about 3 and 4%. Different methods like addition of nucleating agents (AlShannaq et al., 2015; Chandrasekaran et al., 2014), nanoparticles (Kumaresan et al., 2013; Sakr et al., 2017), micro / nano encapsulation (Milián et al., 2017) and application of ultrasonic wave or electric charges (Okawa et al., 2010; Hossain et al., 2015) have been attempted by the researchers on development of functional latent heat storage materials with a target of eliminating the subcooling of PCMs [17-24].

A specific additive cannot be taken for the sake of reducing the degree of subcooling, as it is influenced by so many parameters like homo/hetero nucleation, rate of cooling and roughness of encapsulation. The addition of nucleating agent with the PCM is an extensive method to reduce the subcooling and these can be either being solid particles or crystals that induce the crystallization of the PCMs. The studies of Chen et al. (2000) exposed the role of different nucleating agents in improving the nucleating probability of water and they reported the effects of cooling rate, dimension of encapsulation, mass of different nucleating agents such as iron ore, iron chip, river sand and Silver iodide on the nucleation of water [25]. Gunther et al. (2017) developed a new algorithm to simulate the subcooling with low cooling rates and validated

their simulated results with the experimental data using sodium acetate trihydrate graphite as the PCM [26]. Milon and Braga (2005) observed no subcooling of water at much lower bath temperature that signifies the role of driving potential between heat transfer fluid (HTF) and the PCM to initiate the nucleation [27].

The solidification characteristics of water has been investigated with the dispersion of different nanoparticles such as alumina (Kole and Dey, 2010; Colla et al., 2017), silicon dioxide (Zhang et al., 2010), titanium oxide (Motahar et al., 2017), copper oxide (Naik et al., 2013), graphene nanoplatelets (GNP) (Liu et al., 2014; Jeong et al., 2013) and multiwall carbon nanotubes (MWCNT) (Temel et al., 2018) in order suppress to the subcooling [28-35]. Though their results are inspiring, but the major problem of particle settlement was observed in most of the studies due to number of repeated charging/discharging thermal cycles. Ushak et al. (2016) explored that the lattice parameters of the crystal structure, solubility, and chemical structure are to be considered for selecting the nucleating agent and the crystal system has no influence on the nucleation of the salt hydrate PCMs [36]. Lu and Tassou (2013) inferred that the addition of silver iodide as the nucleating agent with water resulted with the substantial reduction of subcooling and makes water as the suitable PCM in the chilled food cabinets of a cold storage unit [37], the only downside being the expense incurred in the preparation of Silver Iodide.

It has been inferred from the literature review that the addition of nanoparticles and nucleating agent is found to be more beneficial towards the sorting out the problems related to subcooling. Considering the pressing need to reduce or eliminate the major problem of subcooling in water, at a minimum cost, the main objective of the present work is to investigate the solidification characteristics of water dispersed with the natural graphite flake additives at various concentrations in a spherical encapsulation for various parameters.

CHAPTER 6

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The addition of natural graphite flakes (NGF) in PCM preparation is generally carried out with a focused attention, as there is a chance for flocculation of additives to occur. In the present study, de-ionized (DI) water is selected as the base PCM and NGF is the additive being used. Each dispersant with the mass concentration of 1%, 2%, and 3% was dispersed in DI water and the following procedure has been adopted to prepare the stable water-based PCM. A known volume of DI water (50 mL, 100 mL) was taken using a standard volumetric flask (Class B type) and the required mass fraction of NGF was measured using an electronic weighing balance (LCGC LCT303). The dispersants of desired mass fraction were mixed with DI water and the mixture was stirred for 15 min using a magnetic stirrer. The sample was then subjected to a probe sonication with the frequency of 15 kHz for duration of 15 min in order to ensure the proper dispersion of nucleating agent in DI water (Fig 6.1). The flow chart of the adopted procedure is given in Fig. 6.2 and the prepared PCM was then injected to spherical encapsulation made up of glass and due care was taken that no air bubbles were entered inside the encapsulation. The glass ball was filled up to 80% of its volume with the PCM to accommodate the change in volume during solidification and a rubber cork was placed at the neck of the spherical glass container to make a seal. The further experimentation of heat transfer characteristics during solidification have been performed to investigate the effect of adding dispersants in water.

Fig 6.1 Probe sonication with a frequency of 15kHz

Fig 6.2 Preparation of water based PCM

CHAPTER 7

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The main objective of current study was to investigate the solidification characteristics of water-based PCM at surrounding refrigerated / heating circulator bath, rectangular acrylic tank, heat bath temperature of $-7\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $-9\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The fabricated test rig consists of a transfer fluid (HTF) circulation unit, camera (Redmi Note 4) and a data logger (Agilent LXI 34972A), as shown in Fig. 7.1. The schematic arrangement of the test rig is shown in Fig. 7.3 and a mixture of water and ethylene glycol (55:45 by volume) was taken as the Heat Transfer Fluid. The acrylic tank has the dimension $19\text{ cm} \times 16\text{ cm} \times 24\text{ cm}$ and is insulated with a 4 cm thick Polyurethane Foam (PUF). The desired temperature of the HTF was attained by using a proportionate temperature differential controller (PTDC), which regulates the output of refrigerating unit and heater unit with a temperature stability of $0.01\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. After achieving the required temperature condition, the HTF was circulated to the tank at a constant flow rate of 3 L/min and all the tube fittings connecting the refrigerating / heating circulator and tank were thermally insulated in order to minimize the energy loss to the surrounding

Two resistance temperature detectors (RTD) were placed inside the HTF bath at different locations (200 mm from the top and 30 mm from the bottom) to monitor and ensure the temperature uniformity of HTF for every 10 s. Three RTDs were placed inside the spherical encapsulation—one is at the center, second and third RTDs are at a distance of 12 mm and 24 mm from the center is shown in Fig. 7.2. All these RTDs were connected to the data logger which can record the signal output with an accuracy of 0.004%. A rubber cork is fitted at the top of the encapsulation to avoid the leakage of the PCM. After attaining the desired

temperature of the HTF, the spherical encapsulation filled with PCM was placed at the center of the acrylic tank. The experiment was performed until the temperature of PCM at the center of the reached to $-4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and the transient temperature variation of the PCM at three different locations were continuously monitored for every 10s. The experiment was performed for bath temperatures of $-7\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $-9\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for both the 50mL and 100mL samples.

Fig 7.1 Experimental Setup

Fig 7.2 Position of RTDs inside the encapsulated sphere

- | | |
|-------------------------------|------------------------------|
| 1. Chiller Unit | 2. PID Controller |
| 3. Connecting tube | 4. Flow Control Valve |
| 5. Pump | 6. Holder Stand |
| 7. Heat Transfer Fluid | 8. HTF container |
| 9. Spherical ball | 10. Data logger |
| 11. Computer | |

Fig 7.3 Schematic diagram of the experimental setup

CHAPTER 8

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The solidification behavior of water, in terms of reduction of subcooling, is presented in this section with the help of T-t history. Fig. 8.1 illustrates the transition temperature variation of DI water at different radial locations inside the spherical encapsulation cooled sensibly from an initial temperature (30 °C) up to density at a bath temperature of $-7\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $-9\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. It has been noticed that DI water inversion temperature of $-4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at the uniform rate in all three locations. The PCM is then subcooled to a temperature of $-5.4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in the metastable liquid region and the nucleation occurs immediately after the end of metastable state due to the formation of the dendritic ice. It is obvious that the latent heat liberated from the dendritic ice is absorbed by subcooled water so that it returns back to solidification temperature. Time taken for complete

Fig 8.1. T-t history of (a) 50mL (b) 100mL of DI water during solidification

solidification is found to be 74.8min after the onset of solidification for bath temperature -7°C for 50mL, while it is 47.6min for bath temperature -9°C for 50mL as shown in Fig 8.1(a). For 100mL encapsulated sphere, it is observed that time taken for complete solidification is found to be 90.7min after the onset of solidification for bath temperature -7°C , while it is 77.3min for bath temperature -9°C , which can be seen from figure 8.1(b). The PCM near the surface got solidified at a temperature faster rate due to negligible conductive resistance offered by the PCM. The solidification experiment was not performed at a surrounding temperature lower than of -7°C , as the experimentation was already done by the same research group (Satishkumar et. al., 2016). From our previous studies on solidification characteristics of water, the chiller unit integrated with CTES system is to be operated at higher evaporation temperature, as the specific energy consumption (SEC) by the chiller unit increase enormously with respect to decrease in evaporation temperature. The energy efficiency of CTES is enhanced by various techniques such as operation of chiller during night time at full load and partial charging and discharging of cool energy. In addition to that an immense potential exists to enhance the energy efficiency of the CTES system through the elimination of subcooling in water with the addition of additives.

T-t history for -7°C , 50mL of PCM with NGF

The sensible cooling of all samples is found to be the same. Nevertheless, the degree of subcooling water decreases with the addition of 1 wt.% of NGF and it starts to solidify at relatively less time, compared to DI water. A new freezing point is observed, as a result of the balances established between the rate of water molecules entering and leaving the solid. The

Fig 8.2. T-t history of (a) 1 wt.% (b) 2 wt.% (c) 3 wt.% of NGF added to 50mL of PCM with external bath temperature $-7\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

plot of Temperature versus time for the solidification of the PCM on the addition of 1 wt.%, 2 wt.%, 3 wt.% is shown in Fig 8.2 (a), (b), (c) respectively. It can be observed that the onset of solidification is at $-1.179\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for the mixture with 3 wt. %, which has the degree of subcooling at $-6.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Duration of solidification of the PCM with 1 wt. % NGF is reduced by 10 min as compared to DI water. It could be explained by predominant effects of high thermal conductivity of NGF, that by virtue of recirculation resulted in high thermal transport properties for the PCM. As a result, the samples took less time of 9.36%, 6.95% and 2.67% to attain the temperature of $-4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

T-t history for -9°C , 50mL of PCM with NGF

Fig 8.3. T-t history of (a) 1 wt.% (b) 2 wt.% (c) 3 wt.% of NGF added to 50mL of PCM with external bath temperature -9°C

As given in the figure 8.3, the onset of solidification occurred at the same temperature at all three various locations, which clearly indicate the presence of homogenous nucleation in water. Time taken for complete solidification is found to be around 3583 seconds after the onset of solidification. The sensible cooling of all samples is found to be the same. Nevertheless, the degree of subcooling water decreases with the addition of 1 wt.% of NGF and it starts to solidify at relatively lower temperature, compared to DI water. A new freezing point is observed, as a result of the balances established between the rate of water molecules entering and leaving the solid. The plot of Temperature versus time for the solidification of the PCM

on the addition of 1 wt.%, 2 wt.%, 3 wt.% is shown in Fig 8.3 (a), (b), (c) respectively. It can be observed that the onset of solidification is at $0.062\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for the mixture with 3 wt. %. Duration of solidification of the PCM with 1 wt. % NGF is reduced by 7.7 min as compared to DI water. It could be explained by predominant effects of high thermal conductivity of NGF, that by virtue of recirculation resulted in high thermal transport properties for the PCM. As a result, the samples took less time of 12.83%, 22.33% and 27.17% for 1 wt.%, 2 wt.%, 3 wt.% respectively to attain the temperature of $-6.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

T-t history for -7°C , 100mL of PCM with NGF

Fig 8.4. T-t history of (a) 1 wt.% (b) 2 wt.% (c) 3 wt.% of NGF added to 100mL of PCM with external bath temperature $-7\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

As given in the figure 8.4, the onset of solidification occurred at the same temperature at all three various locations, which clearly indicate the presence of homogenous nucleation in water.

Time taken for complete solidification is found to be 78 min after the onset of solidification. The sensible cooling of all samples is found to be the same. Nevertheless, the degree of subcooling water decreases with the addition of 1 wt.% of NGF and it starts to solidify at relatively lower temperature, compared to DI water. A new freezing point is observed, as a result of the balances established between the rate of water molecules entering and leaving the solid. The plot of Temperature versus time for the solidification of the PCM on the addition of 1 wt.%, 2 wt.%, 3 wt.% is shown in Fig 8.4 (a), (b), (c) respectively. It can be observed that the onset of solidification is at 0.055 °C for the mixture with 3 wt.%. Duration of solidification of the PCM with 1 wt. % NGF is reduced by 9.7 min as compared to DI water. It could be explained by predominant effects of high thermal conductivity of NGF, that by virtue of recirculation resulted in high thermal transport properties for the PCM. As a result, the samples took less time of 12.44%, 20.89% and 25.38% for 1 wt.%, 2 wt.%, 3 wt.% respectively to attain the temperature of -4 °C.

T-t history for -9°C , 100mL of PCM with NGF

As given in the figure 8.3, the onset of solidification occurred at the same temperature at all three various locations, which clearly indicate the presence of homogenous nucleation in water. Time taken for complete solidification is found to be 60 min after the onset of solidification. The sensible cooling of all samples is found to be the same. Nevertheless, the degree of subcooling water decreases with the addition of 1 wt.% of NGF and it starts to solidify at relatively lower temperature, compared to DI water. A new freezing point is observed, as a result of the balances established between the rate of water molecules entering and leaving the solid. The plot of Temperature versus time for the solidification of the PCM on the addition of 1 wt.%, 2 wt.%, 3 wt.% is shown in Fig 8.5 (a), (b), (c) respectively. It can be observed that

the onset of solidification is at 0.085°C for the mixture with 3 wt.%. Duration of solidification of the PCM with 1 wt. % NGF is reduced by around 8.2 min as compared to DI water. It could be explained by predominant effects of high thermal conductivity of NGF, that by virtue of recirculation resulted in high thermal transport properties for the PCM. As a result, the samples took less time of 13.67%, 23.17% and 28.16% for 1 wt.%, 2 wt.%, 3 wt.% respectively to attain the temperature of -6.5°C .

Fig 8.5. T-t history of (a) 1 wt.% (b) 2 wt.% (c) 3 wt.% of NGF added to 100mL of PCM with external bath temperature -9°C

CHAPTER 9

CONCLUSIONS

- The onset of solidification depends on cooling rate and water molecules triggers the nucleation at a lower cooling rate at a given sample size. Enthalpy of melting and freezing is reduced with addition of NGF and hence the mass fraction of dispersants needs to be optimized for attaining the desired phase change properties of the PCMs.
- The reduction in solidification time upon the addition of NGF could be explained by predominant effects of high thermal conductivity of NGF, that by virtue of recirculation within the PCM, resulted in improved thermal transport properties for the PCM
- It is concluded that the synergetic effects of reduction of subcooling combined with the enhancement of thermal properties, due to the addition of Natural graphite flakes will be helpful to march forwards towards the development of energy efficient CTES system using water based PCMs for various applications.

CHAPTER 10

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